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People Who Live in Families With Low Work Intensity in Europe

Between 2015 and 2021 they decreased by 21.78%

The Eurostat calculates the index of people who live in families with low work intensity in Europe. Specifically, these are people having a age between 0 and 64 years of age and who live within families where adults work at most 20% of their potential work time. By adults we mean people with one age between 18 and 64 years old. In addition, students are also included in the indicator aged between 18 and 24, people who receive pensions, and people having a age between 60 and 64 years old who live in families where income is the main source of income.

Ranking of countries by number of people who live in families with low work intensity in 2021. Ireland is in the first place among countries by number of people who live in low -intensity families in 2021 with an amount of 13, 00, followed by Greece with a value of 12.10 units and Belgium with a value of 11.90. In the middle of the standings there are Lithuania with 7.80, followed by Croatia with an amount of 7.50 units and by Austria with an amount of 7.60 units. Poland close the ranking with a value of 4.20 units, followed by Slovenia with a value of 3.60 units and Romania with a value of 3.50 units. On average in 2021 for the countries considered about 7.66% of the European population lived in families with low work intensity.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of the number of people who live in families with low work intensity in the transition between 2010 and 2021. France is in the first place for growth of the percentage value of people who live in families with low intensity of work with an amount equal to 28.92% equal to an amount of 2.4 units, followed by Austria with a value of 17.46% equal to an amount of 1.00 units and Sweden with an amount of 14.1% equal to a value of 1.1 units. In the middle of the standings there are Belgium with an amount of -20.67% equal to an amount of -3.1 units, followed by Greece with a value of -20.92% equal to an amount of -3.2 units, followed by Spain with a value of -24.68% equal to an amount of -3.8 units. Romania closes the ranking with an amount of -43.55% equal to an amount of -2.7 units, followed by Cyprus with an amount of -44.23% equal to an amount of -4.6 units and from Portugal with a value of -48.04% equal to an amount of -4.9 units. Overall, between 2015 and 2021 the number of people living in families with low work intensity has decreased by 9.79% of up to 7.66% or 21.78% equal to -2.13 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Three Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Bulgaria, Denmark, Netherlands, Croatia, Lithuania, Italy, Germany, Finland, Cover, Sweden, France;

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- Cluster 2: Greece, Belgium, Ireland, Spain;
- Cluster 3: Poland, Estonia, Romania, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Slovenia, Hungary, Malta, Austria, Luxembourg, Latvia, Portugal.

If we consider the value of the median, the following system of the Clusters or $C2 = 12 > C1 = 8.6 > C3 = 5.3$ is the following system. From a geographical point of view, it is possible to verify that the dominant cluster or the Cluster 2 consists of a mix of European countries not neighboring each other, followed by Cluster 1 which brings together some countries of the center and northern Europe and by the cluster 3 that concerns the Eastern Europe countries. It follows that it is Western Europe that has a problem of people who live in low-intensity families contrary to the countries of Eastern Europe who instead have the most reduced variable values.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the Euclidean distance. Specifically, a complex network structure and four simplified network structures are identified. The complex network structure is constituted as follows or:

- There is a connection between Estonia and Poland with an amount of 0.35 units, and between Estonia and Romania with an amount of 0.35 units;
- Romania has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.35 units, and with Poland for an amount of 0.26 units;
- Poland has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.35 units, with Romania for an amount of 0.26 units, with Slovakia for an amount of 0.4 units and with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.37 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Poland for an amount equal to 0.4 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Poland for an amount of 0.37 units, and with Slovenia for an amount of 0.32 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.32 units.

In addition, there are the following structures with simplified networks or:

- Denmark and Bulgaria have a connection for an amount of 0.39 units;
- Malta and Hungary have a connection for a value of 0.27 units;
- Greece and Belgium have a connection for 0.24 units;
- Italy and Finland have a connection for 0.22 units.

Conclusions. The value of people who live in families with low work intensity has decreased between 2015 and 2021 in the European countries considered. However, it must be considered that in 2021 about 7.6% of the European population lived in families with low work intensity. Furthermore, paradoxically, the percentage growth of people who live in families with low work intensity has been more marked in European countries with medium-high income of income or France with +28.92%, Austria with 17.46% , Sweden with 14.1% and Luxembourg with +1.85%. In other countries there has been a significant reduction in people who live in families with low work intensity. It is necessary to reflect better on the reasons that lead to the presence of low work intensity. As seen by the cluster analysis, western Europe suffers from low work intensity much more than Eastern Europe. This distinction may be since in Western Europe the primary and secondary sector have stopped producing jobs. In addition, the work in the tertiary sector, and above all the advanced tertiary sector, is increasingly exclusive and elitist, following the request for study qualifications and very high professional certifications. It follows that people who live in families with low work intensity are also people who could have problems in accessing professional training and educational paths that could grow the perspectives of employability. It is therefore necessary to invest more in professional paths

for unemployed and under-occupied, through the use of e-learning tools, to allow the acquisition of soft and hard skills that can allow a recovery of employment for those who suffer for low working intensity.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

